

MOLECULAR PROPERTIES OF AN APULIAN ISOLATE OF GRAPEVINE RUPESTRIS STEM PITTING-ASSOCIATED VIRUS FROM *VITIS VINIFERA*

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Grapevine rupestris stem pitting-associated virus (GRSPaV, genus *Foveavirus*, family *Betaflexiviridae*) is known as one of the most common viruses of grapevine, widely distributed in many, if not all, grape-growing areas of the world (Meng *et al.*, 2007; Lima *et al.*, 2009). It is associated with disorders known as rupestris stem pitting (RSP) and vein necrosis (VN).

Following the first description of the virus (Zhang *et al.*, 1998) molecular investigations have led to the complete sequencing of six viral strains denoted GRSPaV-1 (AF057136), GRSPV (AF026278), GRSPaV-SG1 (AY881626), GRSPaV-BS (AY881627), GRSPaV-SY (AY368590) and GRSPaV-PN (AY368172).

We now report the full-length genome sequencing of a new viral isolate from a *Vitis vinifera* accession of cv. Moscato Giallo (GRSPaV-MG), from Apulia (southern Italy).

To this aim, viral dsRNA extracts from cortical scrapings of dormant canes were used as templates for RT-PCR amplification of several fragments spanning the whole genome. Upstream and downstream primers were designed by aligning previously published GRSPaV nucleotide sequences. All PCR amplicons obtained, were cloned using the Strataclone kit (Stratagene, USA) and the resulting plasmids were submitted to automated sequencing.

The complete sequence was 8,722 nt long, excluding the polyA tail, and had a 43% GC content. ORF finder analysis (NCBI Web server) showed that the structural organization of the genome of our viral isolate was identical to that of previously investigated GRSPaV isolates, as it comprises six putative open reading frames (ORFs) plus a 5' and 3' non-coding regions (NCRs) of 60 nt and 139 nt, respectively.

In particular, ORF 1 codes for a polypeptide of 2,161 aa, putatively identified as the replicase, gene whereas ORFs 2, 3 and 4 code, in the order, for three proteins (221 aa; 116 aa; 80 aa) recognized as the triple gene block (TGB) of foveaviruses.

ORF 5 codes for the 259 aa capsid protein (CP) and is followed by ORF 6 which significantly overlaps the CP gene and codes for a protein of 119 aa in size. This latter 3' most ORF, putatively coding for a protein with nucleic acid binding properties, had previously been detected in other members of the family *Flexiviridae* (Zhang *et al.*, 1998; Gentil *et al.*, 2001; Lima *et al.*, 2009).

Assembled sequence data were analysed using the BioEdit 7.0.9 program (Ibis Biosciences, USA) in comparison with the published sequences of the six GRSPaV genomes. Sequence identity among isolates at the nucleotide level ranged from 76% (strain GRSPaV-PN) to 94% (strain GRSPaV-SG1). Identities at the amino acid level substantially confirmed these values, for they ranged from 85 to 94%.

The close relationship with strain GRSPaV-SG1 was confirmed when each single ORF was analysed. Nucleotide sequence identity between our isolate and GRSPaV-SG1 ranged from 96% for the most conserved ORF5, to 94% for ORF 1, which appeared to be the most variable, in accordance with earlier reports (Lima *et al.*, 2009).

The present data confirm the widespread presence in southern Italy of GRSPaV isolates with significant phylogenetic relationship with GRSPaV-1, as ascertained in a recent survey (Morelli *et al.*, 2009).

Key words: *Vitis vinifera*, GRSPaV, Foveavirus, *Grapevine rupestris stem pitting-associated virus*

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References

- GENTIT P., X. FOISSAC, L. SVANELLA-DUMAS, M. PEYPELUT, T. CANDRESSE, 2001. Characterization of two different Apricot latent virus variants associated with peach asteroid spot and Peach sooty ringspot diseases. *Archives of Virology*, **146**, 1453-1464.
- LIMA M., R. ALKOWNI, J.K.UYEMOTO, A. ROWHANI, 2009. Genomic study and detection of a new variant of grapevine rupestris stem pitting-associated virus in declining California pinot noir grapevines. *Journal of Plant Pathology*, **91**, 155-162.
- MENG B., D. GONSALVES, 2007. *Grapevine rupestris stem pitting-associated virus*: a decade of research and future perspectives. *Plant Viruses*, **1**, 52-62.
- MORELLI M., A. MINAFRA, D. BOSCIA, 2009. molecular variability and seed transmission of *grapevine rupestris stem pitting-associated virus* isolates from southern Italy. In: Atti del XV Congresso Nazionale della Società Italiana di Patologia Vegetale, Locorotondo 28 settembre-1 ottobre 2009, 154.
- ZHANG Y.P., J.K. UYEMOTO, A. GOLINO, D.A. ROWHANI, 1998. Nucleotide sequence and RT-PCR detection of a virus associated with grapevine rupestris stem-pitting disease. *Phytopathology*, **88**, 1231-1237.